

GENDEROLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF EMOTIONAL EXPRESSIVENESS

Gulmira Akramjonovna Turdieva

Fergana State University

Annotation

It is known that regardless of the gender or ethnic group of the speaker, the same linguistic system is used for everyone. However, each person's speech and linguistic abilities and abilities are different. In particular, it is not difficult to understand the significant differences in the speech of men and women in expressing inner feelings during communication. This paper widely presents genderological analysis of emotional expressiveness.

Key words: *gender, genderological, emotion, expression, men, women, speech.*

On the one hand, women, especially in Uzbek folk culture, is viewed as weak, vulnerable, and needing constant attention from the opposite sex, lacking the ability to make independent decisions. On the other hand, they are seen as charming, daring, naturally emotional, and full of emotions. The expression of truth, inner experiences, feelings, and their transfer into language are fundamentally different in women and men. In both cultures, in most cases, men's speech differs from women's speech in its lack of emotional coloring. Men have a stronger tendency to dominate, they speak in a loud voice, but not in a state of (positive) emotional states. Women are more emotional, gentle, sensitive to the feelings of others, prone to lies, and passive. In fact, women talk more than men and are more prone to emotional expressiveness.

In this regard, Bekmirzayev's treatise "Orator and Speech" cites the following ideas: "Women are more likely to lie than men, because from a young age they rely more on facial and muscular expressions and turn to the mirror more often than men. For this reason, they are easily deceived by looking straight into the eyes of their interlocutor" (Bekmirzayev, 2015). As we have already emphasized, women are more emotional than men, and we can observe greater restraint and restraint in men. The difference in female and male speech is instilled in their minds from childhood and becomes characteristic of their gender. Girls grow up with a soft nature from a young age, while boys are inclined to give orders, instructions, and leadership. In the girls' speech, gentleness, closeness, and along with this, submissiveness are evident.

In her book "Gender and Emotion", Iona Lattu says: "Our nonverbal behaviors, including facial expressions and tone of voice, can also convey information about our emotional state. Research shows that the nonverbal expression of emotional state in men and women is fundamentally different. In general, women are more emotionally expressive than men, but the way emotions are expressed nonverbally and verbally varies between the sexes. For example, women express joy and sadness more than men, while men express anger more than women (Lattu, 2013).

It should be noted that the expressiveness of women's emotional state does not always manifest itself in the same way as the attributes that are given. In this regard, we turned to the research conducted by psychologists Condry and Ross. The scientists observed the emotional states of two men and two women who were arguing with each other. They first focused on a fight between two men, and then on a fight between two women. They expected the most intense aggression and anger to occur in the first pair, but the development of events did not go as expected: the disagreement between the two women was even more aggressive and pathetic than the disagreement between the two men, that is, women showed more anger and abusive language than men. In fact, although

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

rudeness, anger, and aggression are often emphasized as male characteristics, studies show that in some cases, women are less able to control and express such negative emotions (Condry & Ross, 1985).

In his book "Language and the Place of Women", English linguist R.Lakoff cites 10 characteristics that are characteristic of women's speech:

1. Lexical hedges or fillers, e.g. *you know, sort of,*
2. Tag questions, e.g. *she is very nice, isn't she?*
3. Rising intonation on declaratives, e.g. *it's really good.*
4. Empty adjectives, e.g. *divine, charming, cute.*
5. Precise color terms, e.g. *magenta, acqamarine.*
6. Intensifiers such as *just* and *so*.
7. Hypercorrect grammar, e.g. *consistent use of standard verb forms.*
8. Superpolite forms, e.g. *indirect requests, euphemisms.*
9. Avoidance of strong swear words, e.g. *fudge, my goodness.*
10. Emphatic stress, e.g. it was a *brilliant* performance (Lakoff, 1975).

As the English researcher Broverman emphasizes, people usually experience different emotions in different situations. However, we can witness that representatives of the opposite sex, even in the same situation, experience different emotions (Broverman, 1972).

The scientist Shevchenko, who has done significant work on gender issues, emphasizes that the status of women depends on their place in society, their position, and their level of education, and writes: "The speech of educated women has intonation integrity. Women with higher education pronounce a larger part of their speech between pauses than women with lower education. "But their speech surpasses that of highly educated men. This indicates that women spend less time thinking" (Shevchenko, 2019).

Numerous social psychological analyses show that while the emotional character traits common to most men include: toughness, aggression, self-confidence, truthfulness, and fearlessness, the qualities common to women include curiosity, alertness, imagination, gentleness, tenderness, humility, and obedience.

We know that determination and fearlessness are considered to be characteristics of men: *game as a cockerel – a brave, courageous, fearless man; a man's man – a real man; play the man – to act like a man; full of bush fire – very energetic, courageous, cheerful; like a Trojan – heroic, courageous.*

But in some places we can also see the characteristics of weakness and indecision in men: *a fall guy – a coward, a coward; play the woman – a fool; have too much of his mother's blessing – to be too shy, mummy's boy – mother's darling, mother's darlings make but milk-soap heroes – mother's darlings don't make heroes, be pinned to one's mother's apron strings – mother's apron strings don't make heroes, a weak sister – a tanned girl, nice Nelly – a two-faced woman.* Judging by the examples given, the negative aspects of men are most often expressed using words related to the semantic field of "woman".

In conclusion, the expression of emotions and their transfer into language differ significantly between men and women. In most cases, men's speech differs from that of the opposite sex in its lack of emotional color.

References:

1. Bekmirzayev, N. (2015) Orator and speech. Navruz, 38-39.
2. Condry, J., Ross, D. (1985) Sex and aggression: The influence of gender label on the perception of aggression in children. *Child Development*, 225-233.
3. Latu., (2013) Gender and emotion. Peter Lang Press, 119.
4. Lakoff, G. (1972) Hedges: A study Of meaning criteria and the logic of fuzzy concepts. Chicago University Press.
5. Shevchenko, I. (2019) Gender features of precarity // *Sociological studies*, 84-95.
5. Broverman, I., Vogel, R. (1972) A current appraisal. *Journal of Social issues*, 59-78.
6. Galperin, I. (1971) *Stylistics*, 62-118.
7. Ginzburg, R. (1979) A course in modern English lexicology, 22.
8. Abdullayev, A. (1987) Syntactic method of expressiveness in Uzbek language, 69.
9. Turdiyeva G. (2022) The interpretation of emotional expressiveness in English and Uzbek languages. *Web of scientist: International scientific research journal*, 3(12), 51-55.
10. Turdiyeva G. (2023) Structural features of lexical units expressing emotions in Uzbek and English languages. *Research Jet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 4(6), 65-69.

